

SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF JEALOUSY AND BETRAYAL IN FAMILY RELATIONSHIPS

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ABSTRACT

This research study conducted a socio-psychological analysis of the problem of jealousy and betrayal in family relationships. The family, as the main social institution of society, is built on mutual respect, trust and love. However, the weakness of communication, different characters and ways of thinking, as well as internal and external pressures create the basis for the emergence of conflicts such as jealousy and betrayal. The feeling of jealousy is considered a psychological phenomenon formed by both biological instinct and social conditions and can manifest itself in the form of blameworthy communication, control, suspicion and emotional manipulation in behavior. Betrayal, on the other hand, occurs due to the incompleteness of intra-family relationships, psychological and physiological incompatibility, lack of love and trust and can lead to family breakdown, emotional trauma and social complications. The study analyzed in detail the motives, complications, preventive measures and recommendations for protecting the family of jealousy and betrayal. The results show that healthy family relationships should be based on understanding the concepts of mutual obligation, trust, communication and responsibility.

Keywords: family, intra-family conflict, jealousy, betrayal, emotional impact, behavioral patterns.

Introduction

In the current conditions, where socio-psychological phenomena are expanding, information technologies are rapidly expanding, and relationships are changing, the socio-psychological analysis of family problems is of great relevance. Changing, updated conditions also radically change the attitude towards family issues. Updated conditions bring new concerns to families and people, along with all their negative and positive features. This necessitates the socio-psychological analysis of numerous family problems in the context of changing socio-political relations.

In modern times, the direction of intra-family conflicts has begun to change. Previously, the problem was more of a "daughter-in-law-in-law" or "daughter-in-law-sister-in-law" relationship, but today, due to the existence of parallel families or interference in relationships by someone outside the family, and consequently, jealousy and betrayal, intra-family conflicts arise, and we even witness divorces. In other words, the scale has changed. One of the factors influencing this is the development of technology. Family psychology emerged with the emergence of cybernetics.

In recent times, there have been fertile conditions for the spread of infidelity. It has become easy for women and men to meet new friends and interlocutors on social networks through mobile phones and establish relationships with them. The expansion of these opportunities causes married couples to constantly be suspicious of each other, and in many cases, unfounded jealousy and suspicion arise. The continuation of such situations ultimately leads to intra-family conflicts and divorce. Such situations are often understood as infidelity.

If we talk about the general problem, family relationships should be transparent and the parties should have a commitment to each other.

The main part

"Family is a small social unit based on marriage or blood kinship, connected by common household and

mutual moral responsibility. It is an important component of the social structure of every society and plays an important role in the development of that society by performing many social functions. The word family comes from the Arabic root (awl), which means to stand - it is used for people who stand and trust each other" [3, p.4].

Family is one of the oldest and most unique forms of human relationships. The uniqueness and self-reliance of family. The fact is that several people spend the vast majority of their lives in close interaction with each other, over a long period of time measured in decades. There have been people in our country who have lived happily together for more than a hundred years.

A truly happy family is one that, despite all the problems, can still maintain their commitment and love for each other.

There are many factors that are causing family ties to break down today. Problems such as disagreements, indecision, misunderstanding, jealousy and betrayal lead to the rupture of family ties. Although these problems may seem like ordinary problems, in reality small shortcomings can lead to big problems. "A family is a small state" - it was not said for nothing. Of course, there are and should be problems in the family. A man and a woman should be able to solve their problems together and understand each other. The modern family model can be different for everyone. The modern family model involves understanding each other. Communication must be established in order to understand each other. By communicating, people can solve all the problems between them. The root of such problems arises from the lack of communication. Mutual respect is necessary in a family. Sometimes we say that love is the main thing, and sometimes we say that respect is the main thing. People get married loving each other, and love later turns into respect. Being loved is a beautiful feeling, including loving.

There may be various differences in the relationships between men and women. Every person's charac-

ter is different. Every person's way of thinking is different. A man and a woman should be able to compromise with each other when solving a problem between them. Sometimes, if one of the two people in a family creates a problem, the other person should not make that problem worse. According to the popular saying, if one is fire, the other should be water. A man and a woman should understand the promise they made to each other when solving a problem between them. Of course, people should get to know each other during the period before marriage. Although this period is called the engagement period, in fact, this period can be called the recognition period. Because couples learn each other's characteristics during this period. It is important to be able to evaluate this period correctly, because it plays the role of the main foundation for subsequent periods. Therefore, this period should be somewhat long, but they should be able to appreciate this period and try to get to know each other well so that in the event of common problems that may arise later, unpleasant and problematic expressions such as "I didn't know you well," "I didn't know you were such a person," or "If I had known it would be like this, I wouldn't have married you" are not used.

One of the factors that causes conflicts within the family is jealousy. Jealousy is one of the most common problems in family relationships. Jealousy is the killer of relationships. It is no coincidence that jealousy is one of the factors that cause couples to argue the most. Jealousy is often observed alongside feelings of worthlessness, unhappiness, loneliness, lack of self-confidence, and helplessness. Jealousy is an emotion that can both lose what you have and desire to possess what someone else has. Jealousy is sometimes observed as a passing moment in everyday life, and sometimes as an emotion that can turn your entire life upside down. Jealousy can often stem from problems that the jealous person exaggerates and interprets in their inner world. Jealousy poisons and destroys the beauty and charm of love (Z.Freud).

"There are people in life who are naturally jealous. Sometimes this feeling arises in them without any reason and does not even need a specific excuse. The reason lies in their inner world, in their nature. Jealousy manifests itself in three ways: a) a man or woman is a little jealous, then realizes that they were wrong and feels remorse, regretting their weakness; b) a man or woman is extremely out of control, does not set limits to their speech and actions; c) a man or woman is content with comforting only themselves. It is a family tragedy when a husband does not believe his wife and makes her feel this not only to him, but also to children, relatives, acquaintances, neighbors and others" [1, p.566].

Jealousy is an emotion that arises from the fear of losing something or someone. The feeling of jealousy is also present in nature. That is, it is not a feeling unique to humans. It can also be easily observed in ordinary domestic animals. When jealousy is in its initial stage and in a weak form, it is normally accepted by people. However, when it reaches a somewhat extreme level, it can create serious problems for both the person himself and others. Even in the criminal code, there are

articles that regulate criminal acts committed on the basis of jealousy.

There are different approaches to the emergence of the feeling of jealousy. Some say that the feeling of jealousy is innate, while others say that it is a feeling that arises later. Considering that the feeling of jealousy manifests itself according to the society in which people live, then we can say that the feeling of jealousy is a feeling that arises later. That is, there must be a reason for jealousy in order for it to arise. For example, the decrease in attention and care for a child who grows up alone at home until the age of 3 due to a new child entering the family causes the feeling of jealousy to manifest itself. A child who has never shown jealousy or has no reason to do so suddenly begins to show severe jealous behaviors.

Jealousy is not an indicator of love in any case. Jealousy is an indicator of doubt and distrust in love. The desire not to lose someone who is valuable to a person and the slight feelings of jealousy that come from this desire are natural and normal. However, most often the intensity of excessive jealousy also shows the extent of the person's own need to be loved. This can manifest itself in reactions such as violence, pressure or resentment, depending on the character traits of people.

Jealousy is an emotional state that arises from unconscious assumptions and is one of the components of incompleteness complexes. Jealousy causes the emergence of negative moods in the form of asthenic and sthenic forms, and if not prevented, it can take a severe form and turn into depressions, even affects. During the emergence of extreme jealousy, suicide, attempts against the jealous person, and attempts against the subject that causes the jealous subject to become jealous can also occur.

It is known from natural observations that if a strange male approaches a herd of animals, the male leading the herd will become angry and exhibit destructive behavior. It is also possible to observe similar situations in the behavior of most people. Therefore, there is a similarity between human jealousy and animal jealousy. This gives grounds to say that jealousy is a biological (innate) instinct. As a biological instinct, jealousy is the fear of losing control over the other party or the other party, losing authority, as well as facing betrayal. When a state of jealousy occurs, the events occurring around are evaluated emotionally, not logically. Since jealousy is an unconscious feeling, its prevention depends on the high level of development of human thinking.

Prominent manifestations of jealousy in behavior. This includes accusatory communication, rude or resentful behavior, suspicious glances, making remarks about a new style of clothing or hairstyle, listening to phone conversations, increased surveillance or stalking, opposing the other party's social interaction, opposing recreational outings or watching the surroundings from the window or balcony, etc.

"The main reasons that cause jealousy are: not being able to meet the needs of the partner as a lover; being dissatisfied with one's own physiological appearance; the partner's appearance attracting the atten-

tion of others; the jealous person's lifestyle that is consistent with the assumptions that give rise to jealousy; the presence of people in the jealous person's circle of communication who live lifestyles that are consistent with the assumptions that give rise to jealousy; having a capricious, obsessive and selfish character; having experienced the trauma of betrayal by loved ones in the past" [5, p.29].

Jealousy should not arise from unfounded fear, it should not lead to accusations of something to the other party over trivial, insignificant things, and small situations, and it should not make family life unlivable for both parties. When a husband and wife are suspicious of each other and jealous, even without any reason or evidence, it is a sign of their lack of trust in each other. It damages the trust and confidence of the spouses, and at the same time, it damages the healthy atmosphere in the family. This type of behavior is considered a form of abuse, which is prohibited in the Holy Quran. No one has the right to accuse another of something without any evidence or proof. Yes, a man should be jealous of his wife, but this jealousy should not go beyond common sense, reason, and logic and lead to inappropriate thoughts and unfounded worries.

It may seem from the outside that men are more jealous. Because when men are jealous, they quickly manifest destructive behavior and do not hesitate to make others feel it. Most women prefer to share this state with their loved ones or do not share it at all. Observations and surveys conducted in the environment give reason to note that women in Azerbaijani families are more jealous of their husbands. This can be explained by the fact that housewives who are not connected with the business environment still constitute the majority in Azerbaijani families, and such women compare various information they receive from their social circles with assumptions, not facts. For this reason, various images and abstract events take root in thinking, and this state enters reality through jealous behavior. For example, a woman remembers what she has heard about unfaithful men or the behavior of unfaithful men in TV series and begins to look for similar situations in her partner. When she sees any behavior in her partner that arouses her suspicions, acts of jealousy begin to emerge, and suspicious assumptions begin to have their consequences in the relationship.

"Psychologists divide people into different groups based on their feelings of jealousy using special tests. At one end of the spectrum are those who are not jealous at all, and at the other end are those whose feelings of jealousy reach a pathological level. Several groups that are considered the norm are located in the intermediate zone. Jealousy, like love, does not remain at the same level permanently, but changes under the influence of various reasons and with age" [4, p.232].

People can carry all their feelings, but if they cannot control and regulate them, it can lead to many psychological problems. Jealousy is one of them. This feeling, when it goes beyond its limits, can deprive you of many things. The most important thing is to from the people you love.

To overcome jealousy, the jealous person must first want it. Then, the root causes of jealousy in that

person should be analyzed together with him or her and the causes that cause jealousy should be combated with a logical approach. Sometimes people's feelings of jealousy, especially in love relationships, are based on previous experiences. However, since this is not understood by the person himself, it becomes difficult to combat the feeling of jealousy that arises from the previous experiences of others or his or her own. Therefore, in order to weaken the feeling of jealousy, the person must first understand the reasons for his or her jealousy.

On the other hand, jealousy is an internal emotion and can manifest itself in various forms of behavior. However, in this case, the parties should treat each other well and maintain sincerity. For this reason, a man who is jealous of his wife should pay attention to her clothing and lifestyle first of all. On the other hand, he should try to keep his wife away from strangers as much as possible. The woman should also ask her husband about this issue. She should always keep her sensitivity in mind. Therefore, she should pay attention to her speech, clothing, actions and behavior, and should not provoke non-mahram men by wearing attractive perfumes. A woman should only dress up for her husband.

Just as every mother is a psychologist for her child, every man or woman should be a psychologist for his or her life partner. If your life is made unbearable by the other person's jealous actions, you should mobilize your spiritual strength to prevent this and develop tactics and strategies that will influence the other person. For example: men or women can create confidence in their partner's loyalty by demonstrating their love for their spouse, emphasizing that they are the most important person in their life, saying kind words, etc. In addition, tell them which actions of the other person make you jealous the most and try to solve them together.

As we have mentioned, the foundation of a family should be built on trust. People do not trust each other, in fact, there should be mutual trust and confidence between married couples. However, people who start a family do not sufficiently consider the legal steps that will insure their future life and do not take steps in this direction. Currently, there is a lot of outside interference in family relations. These range from kinship relations to social networks. If in the past, the emphasis in the family was on strengthening family values, now these steps play a more destructive role.

The problem of infidelity in the family arises from the crisis of family relationships. If a person does not find spiritual, psychological, physiological understanding, and peace of mind at home, then of course he will seek solace outside of himself.

Currently, we observe that men are most tolerant in order to prevent the family from falling apart. Another situation is when both parties betray and turn it into the norm. Thus, even these relationships have become seriously asocial. Now the increase in betrayal among women is a serious signal, and its prevention can be possible with the understanding of mutual obligation and responsibility. By the way, there are many

parties who do not consciously enter into family formation with a sense of obligation and responsibility. This is just like a mission to increase the number of generations. Families are formed either on the basis of romance - love, passion, or at the insistence of the parents of the parties.

Betrayal is a very relevant topic today. Not everyone betrays, does not attempt betrayal. Not everyone takes such a risk. Usually, people who betray do not do it for the first time. It is a habit for them. The character of a person who betrays their spouse is not fully formed. The person who betrays does not know exactly what he wants. Such a person has no understanding of the strength of family ties. Nothing is sacred for them. Or the person who betrays does so because he has a psychological problem. Why does he have a psychological problem? Either he punishes his wife at home, or he punishes himself, or he does not value himself to such an extent that he says to himself, "You deserve such a life" and takes this step.

People who cheat are people who are not resistant to stress. They do not keep their word. At the same time, they normalize betrayal in their own eyes. Knowing that betrayal is very serious and has a deadly effect on the other party, they still normalize these actions.

Some men who cheat subconsciously take revenge on their spouses. Such men are dissatisfied with their family life for some reason. They do not solve this problem, the point that worries them at home, but rather with their wives, they become angry, resentful, and decide to pay for it with betrayal. How much psychological problem does a person have to have to take a step like betrayal? First of all, a man or a woman should look at their own behavior and family before committing betrayal. Probably, there are mistakes on both sides. A person can make a mistake knowingly or unknowingly. But what is this mistake? If a person takes a step without telling the other person what to do, it will lead to betrayal. If they solve the problem in the family together, if they find the root of the problem together, of course it will not end in betrayal. No, if they are lazy and say, "He won't understand me anyway. How does he know what I want?", of course it will end in betrayal. This applies to both men and women.

"Infidelity to one's spouse is called adultery (fr. adultere). Adultery is used to mean a married person having sexual intercourse with another married or unmarried person. This process can be accidental or habitual. The motives for infidelity vary depending on age, individual, and sexual factors.

With the motive of betrayal The motives include the motive of psychological and physiological incompatibility between husband and wife; the motive of self-affirmation of masculinity; the motive of self-affirmation of femininity; the motive of inclination to sexual adventures and impressions; the motive of punishing the spouse for any dissatisfaction; the motive of irreconcilability with the loss of independence of celibacy (or lack of understanding of family responsibility); the motive of increasing or improving sexual experience; betrayal motivated by threat; mania; falling under the influence (or the principle of "staying away from

friends"); long-term separation of spouses, etc. [5, p.44-49].

If there is a lack of desire, insatiable love between husband and wife, and at the same time, the needs in intimate relationships are not met, they should still talk about it together and solve it. A person who cheats should know that he is cheating on himself. This is understood in psychology as a person punishing himself.

In most cases, a man's betrayal of his family Adultery is considered forgivable, while female infidelity is considered a terrible sin. Those speaking from the context of gender equality do not consider this correct and emphasize that representatives of both sexes bear equal responsibility.

The betrayal of one of the partners by his spouse reveals the incompleteness of their relationship, the hidden tendency to alienation. Psychologists emphasize that betrayal strengthens the feeling of indifference, resentment and regret. Those who are betrayed in the family sooner or later find out about it and at this time experience a deep emotional and psychological shock. The betrayal of both a woman and a man leads to a deep crisis in the family, a loss of mutual trust, and the family is faced with the threat of disintegration.

"The roots of male infidelity lie in being alone during business trips and vacations, alcohol intoxication, and love for another woman, while the roots of female infidelity lie in dissatisfaction with intimate life in the family, sympathy for another man, and a tendency to be pampered with gifts and money" [2, p.292].

Unfortunately, in society, it is said as a "diagnosis" that men cheat. Women cheat too. It's just that these things are kept secret. But there is a saying that has become common: "Men cheat. Men cheat, of course, with women. So women cheat too. Women are able to hide it subtly. Men are not able to hide it. Perhaps women pay more attention to the little things and investigate and find out if a man is cheating. Men are not strong enough to hide their feelings and their betrayal is exposed."

A woman who is faced with her husband's betrayal perceives herself as humiliated and insulted, no longer loved. Betrayal inflicts an irreparable wound on a woman's psyche. However, women do not forgive what happened once and console themselves with the words "Whatever, in the end he came back to me."

Women cheat because they are unhappy with their spouses: "A woman may be dissatisfied with her husband, because no one is perfect. Express your dissatisfaction, give him a chance to improve. Also, betrayals that arise due to lack of self-confidence are more terrible. She cannot speak her mind to a family member at home. She cannot find the strength in herself to solve her problem with her husband. She gets angry by betraying her husband. But she finds the strength in herself to betray. This is a paradoxical situation!

One of the reasons for infidelity is a health problem in the spouse. If a woman or a man is not strong enough and cannot provide for their partner, in these cases Betrayal also happens. Of course, this doesn't apply to everyone, but one type of betrayal is also related to one of the parties being ill.

In order for a person not to betray, moral values and family ties should be important to him. He should think that if he breaks his spouse's trust and confidence once, his spouse will not treat him the same way as before. Their families may fall apart. If they have children, they will experience severe trauma. It is very important to form the right family model to protect themselves from betrayal. In general, if a person's family is sacred, betrayal is tantamount to death. Betrayal seems to him like unbearable suffering and torture.

"Infidelity leads to various complications: divorce occurs; psychological well-being is disrupted (stressful life is experienced); the number of family conflicts increases; the likelihood of illness entering the family increases; the social status of the family is affected; parent-child relationships are disrupted; suicidal thoughts increase or suicide attempts occur in the person experiencing the shock of infidelity; actions are taken to harm the mental or physical health of the infidel and his lover (lover); the risk of the infidel being killed increases; the number of children with mental trauma and complexes increases" [5, p.49-50].

To prevent infidelity, it is necessary to periodically clarify the risk probabilities of infidelity, eliminate the factors that cause these probabilities, and deeply study the psychological characteristics of the other party. It is necessary to plant and adapt to it, create an environment of high psychological calm in the family, organize frequent family outings, have positive conversations about the family's perspective, avoid annoying scenes of jealousy, make changes in appearance that will arouse the sexual feelings of the other party, make them feel that sexual relations are born of love, organize conversations on intimate topics to learn about the other party's sexual desires, demands, and fantasies, and build sexual relations in this direction.

Different people have different attitudes towards the breakdown of their personal family life. Everyone experiences this crisis in their own way. The failure of hopes for family life, the emergence of many qualities in their spouse that they do not desire and find unbearable, is difficult for everyone. At this time, the spiritual and moral crisis that a person faces seems to freeze their life. As a result of the crisis in the family, a person who feels lonely and abandoned falls into great despair, tension, fatigue, indifference to themselves, their close circle, and work become their way of life for a while.

If a husband and wife show kindness and loyalty to each other from the first day of marriage, the family will be happy and long-lived. A spouse is decisive in the future fate of not only a woman or a man, but also children, such as father and mother. That is why every young person should know who they are marrying and living with, what characteristics they have, and how to take these characteristics into account in family life? However, sometimes these important aspects are not taken into account, and external attractiveness, casual communication, etc. result in starting a family.

The preservation of the family depends largely on the understanding of family responsibility. To allow betrayal means to put the family face to face with its disintegration.

Family is an environment where nothing can be achieved alone. If both parties have taken this responsibility upon themselves, it is their duty to continue it to the end. As they say, family is unity, family is a small society.

Conclusion

The research paper reflects the socio-psychological analysis of the problem of jealousy and betrayal, which is relevant for the modern era. This problem is one of the factors that cause intra-family conflicts.

The research study reflected the behavioral manifestations of jealousy, the main causes that cause it, the motives of betrayal, its consequences, preventive measures against it, etc. In order to protect the family and eliminate problems, it was considered important for the parties to understand each other, find the root of the problem, and for both parties to examine their own behavior, including understanding mutual obligations and family responsibility.

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